

Kidney Disease Analysis Using WEKA

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Abstract: The paper describes the kidney disease analysis. Chronic Kidney Disorder affects one in every five men and one in every four women globally between the ages of 65 and 74. (CKD). 10% of the population worldwide is affected by (CKD), and millions die each year due to lack of access to affordable treatment. A protein present in urine, persistent proteinuria is a key indicator for the presence of CKD. Early identification can help prevent kidney disease from progressing to renal failure. This detection and subsequent prevention can be achieved by applying Data Mining techniques on patient information to predict the occurrence of chronic kidney disease. This analysis covers statistic data along with historic and medical details. The dataset contains data of 400 samples with their ages ranging between 2-90 years. An estimate can be drawn in relation to the seriousness of certain circumstances after a decision has been made.

I. INTRODUCTION

Chronic kidney disease (CKD) is a significant public health problem worldwide, especially for low- and medium-income countries. Chronic kidney disease (CKD) means that the kidney does not work as expected and cannot correctly filter blood. Around 10% of the world's population has (CKD), and millions die each year due to a lack of inexpensive treatment options, with the number of older people increasing. According to the Global Burden Disease 2010 study conducted by the International Society of Nephrology, chronic kidney disease (CKD) has been raised as an important cause of mortality worldwide with in the last two decades, the number of deaths has increased by 82.3 percent. Also, the number of patients reaching end-stage renal disease (ESRD) is increasing, which requires kidney transplantation or dialysis to save patients' lives.

CKD, in its early stages, has no symptoms; testing may be the only way to find out if the patient has kidney disease. Early identification of CKD in its early stages can assist patients receive appropriate treatment and avoid the development of ESRD [1]. It is suggested that everyone with one of the CKD risk factors, such as a family history of renal failure, hypertension, or diabetes, have their

kidneys tested once a year. The sooner they know about having this disease, the sooner they can get treatment. To raise awareness and to encourage those who are most susceptible to the disease to perform the tests

periodically, we hope that the disease can be detected with the least possible tests and at low cost. As a result, the goal of this study is to develop an effective model for predicting CKD using the fewest possible indicators.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Gunarathne W.H.S.D et al. [1] compared the outcomes of various models. And finally, they concluded that the Multiclass Decision Forest algorithm gives more accuracy than other algorithms which is around 99% for the reduced dataset of 14 attributes.

S.Ramya and Dr.N.Radha [2] worked on diagnosis time and improvement of diagnosis accuracy using different classification algorithms of machine learning. The proposed work deals with classification of different stages of CKD according to its gravity. By analysing different algorithms like Basic Propagation Neural Network, RBF and RF. The results of the investigation show that the RBF algorithm outperforms the other classifiers, with an accuracy of 85.3 percent.

Missing values in a chronic renal disease dataset were investigated by S. Dilli Arasu and Dr. R. Thirumalaiselvi [3]. Missing values in the dataset will reduce the model's accuracy as well as the accuracy of the prediction outputs. They discovered a solution to this difficulty by performing a recalculation process on CKD stages, which resulted in unknown values. They recalculated missing data to fill up the gaps.

They employ a unique strategy to identify CKD using a machine learning algorithm, Asif Salkin and John Stankovic [7]. They get results from a dataset with 400 records and 25 variables that indicate whether a patient has CKD or not. To get results, they use k-nearest neighbours, random forest, and neural networks. They employ a wrapper strategy to reduce the number of features, which allows them to detect CKD with high accuracy.

Pinar Yildirim [8] investigates the impact of class imbalance when using a neural network algorithm to train data for making medical decisions about chronic kidney disease. A comparison research was conducted utilising a sampling algorithm in this proposed work. The use of sampling algorithms can increase the effectiveness of classification algorithms, according to this study. It also shows that the learning rate is an

important element that has a big impact on multilayer perceptrons.

III.METHODOLOGY

Dataset and Attributes: There are 400 patient records in this dataset. In addition, they have 25 properties, but we only use 14 for our model. Age, Blood Pressure, Albumin, Red Blood Cells, Pus Cells, Pus Cell Clumps, Serum Creatinine, Haemoglobin, White Blood Cell Count, Red Blood Cell Count, Anaemia, Classification, Appetite, and Packed Cell Volume are all 14 characteristics that are utilised to create a model.

Data Description

Cleaning the data: Collect open-source raw data on CKD patients from the internet. Because the data we acquired from the internet did not include the attribute's name, we initially provided names to the attribute. Missing values in the dataset, such as NAs or blank values, are replaced with the attribute's mean values using the WEKA function "Replace Missing Values."

Training and Testing Dataset

The dataset is separated into two subsets, each with 14 properties. The training dataset is derived from the main dataset and contains 300 of the 400 items in the CKD main dataset. Data for testing: 100 out of 400 records from the core CKD dataset were used in the testing.

Classifiers:

Decision Tree: A choice tree is a graphical depiction of a specific decision circumstance that is utilised in a predictive model. The root, nodes, and branching decision are the essential components of a decision tree. In areas of medical science where a large number of parameters are involved in the classification of a data set, a decision tree is used. Because decision trees are the most compressive of all machine learning algorithms.

Support Vector Machine: SVM (Support Vector Machine) is a supervised machine learning technique that may be used to solve both classification and regression problems. It is, however, mostly employed to solve categorization difficulties. The value of each feature is the value of a particular coordinate in this technique, which plots each data item as a point in n-dimensional space (where n is the number of characteristics you have). Then we accomplish classification by locating the hyperplane that best distinguishes the two classes. Simply put, support vectors are the coordinates of each individual observation.

IV. IMPLEMENTATION

- ★ Analyzing using Weka:

- Download and install the Weka tool if it is not installed.
- Once the install is finished, we can change to its directory and launch Weka.

- Download the dataset
 - Add downloaded dataset to weka/data.
 - If the dataset is .csv type change to .arff type.
 - Add that .arff datatype to weka/data.
- Open Explorer

- Open file->Run the dataset

- It will show the attributes, minimum, maximum, mean and stdDev
- It will also show a graphical representation
 - Blue indicates the unsuccessful classification
 - Red indicates the successful classification

- Choose any algorithm to classify the dataset
- Here, J48 decision tree algorithm is used
- To run J48 tree select classify->choose->trees->J48
- Choose the test option to run

- Here we used J48 decision tree
- J48 doesn't run numeric attributes it only takes nominal attributes
- Select a nominal attribute that you want and click the start button
- It will show the Correctly Classified Instances and Incorrectly Classified Instances

- We can run the datasets using different algorithm J48 is one method.
- We can also visualize the tree click on the result list select one attribute and right click on it choose the option visualize tree

V. CONCLUSION

This study looks at the capacity of machine learning algorithms to detect CKD using the fewest possible tests or features. On a small dataset of 400 records, we used four machine learning classifiers to accomplish this goal: logistic regression, SVM, random forest, and gradient boosting. The relationship between variables has been investigated in order to reduce the number of features and remove redundancy. The remaining attributes were put through a filter feature selection technique, which demonstrated that haemoglobin, albumin, and specific gravity have the greatest influence on CKD prediction.

By utilising 10-fold cross-validation, the classifiers were trained, tested, and validated. By F1-measure (99.1 percent), sensitivity (98.8 percent), and specificity (98.8 percent), the gradient boosting technique provided better results (99.3 percent). This is the best outcome among earlier experiments with fewer features and, as a result, lower costs. As a result, we believe that only three characteristics can be used to identify CKD.

VI. REFERENCES

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